

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF MUSIC LESSONS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of organizing and conducting music lessons in preschools. It also explains how important music is for children.*

Keywords: *music, ancestry, generation, upbringing, aesthetic, democratic, art, inner, society, child, heart, spirituality.*

INTRODUCTION

The future and tomorrow of Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without young people. The art of music in youth education has a direct and strong influence on a person from a young age and occupies a great place in his general cultural development. Music, which occupies a wider place in the cultural life of a democratic society, is a constant companion of a person throughout his life. Music is the only art that penetrates deeply into the human heart and has the power to vividly express this soul. So, it is true that music has a worthy role in raising a generation worthy of our ancestors, and doing the honorable job of aesthetic education of a child is a great responsibility for us, i.e. future personnel.

Preschool education aims to form a healthy and mature personality of the child, while preparing him for school. Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states: "Education up to the age of 6-7 is provided in the family, kindergarten and other educational institutions, regardless of the form of ownership. will be carried out," it was noted. In fact, the earlier the education starts, the earlier its effect will be manifested and it will have a positive effect on the whole way of life of a person.

To improve the system of preschool education, to ensure the advantage of the proper organization of the educational process by educators, its control by responsible persons, for the parents of preschool children to engage in child education in the family. In order to create convenience, the basic program "First Step" was developed on the basis of the Law "On Education", the National Program of Personnel Training, the Concept of Preschool Education, and the State requirements for the development of preschool children.

The content of the program is based on the principle of psycho-physiological development of children, and involves their interaction with events and objects in the world, as well as with various fields. In the program, Uzbek folklore, folk games, music, dances, works of applied art and nature are given great importance. At the same time, the program envisages raising a sense of respect for other nations, and special emphasis is placed on teaching children kindness, beauty and benevolence. In the implementation of the program, it is important to strengthen the physical and mental health of children, to form the basis of movement and hygienic skills. The program envisages providing children with valeological education: the child will have ideas about a healthy lifestyle, understand the importance of hygienic and movement culture, protect health, protect the

body, provide the necessary help to oneself and others in time. such as knowledge means that the child's personal culture, social protection.

Methodology of organizing music classes and state requirements of preschool education based on the competency approach. Minimum requirements for the level of preparation of students during preschool education. The minimum amount of educational content in the subject of the methodology of conducting music lessons. Competencies that students should acquire in music classes. Content, essence and analysis of the music education program. Analysis of training. "Ilk Kadam" is a state document developed for pre-school educational institutions, which envisages the educational and educational work of the music director, and prepares children for school education. When planning music classes, the pedagogue should take into account the mental, physical, and emotional burdens of children and, accordingly, should correctly arrange the sequence of the repertoire and types of activities to be taught.

Every music leader needs to know how to make effective use of exhibitions so that every music lesson is interesting and long-lasting in the children's memory. When organizing a lesson, the music director should not forget the following:

1. training report, new song, dance moves, exhibitions prepared for used musical instruments;
2. being able to connect parts together;
3. communicate in a simple and low tone in order to interest children, taking into account their age characteristics;
4. being able to use technical means;
5. to strengthen children's knowledge and skills with the help of musical educational and didactic games;
6. organization of musical action games using props and toys.

Music classes are activities that provide appropriate and comprehensive education and training for each child's musical ability. Various types of activities are integrated in them: singing, performing rhythmic movements, listening to music, introducing music literacy. Playing music makes children more active. Organized holidays will be more interesting and successful.

Music lessons are held simultaneously with the whole group. Its content and structure depends on the age of the children and the assigned tasks.

It is conducted in small groups for 15-20 minutes.

It takes 20-25 minutes in the middle group.

It is conducted in a large group for 25-30 minutes.

It takes 30-35 minutes in the preparation group.

Music lessons are held twice a week. All children of the group participate in it. Music lessons include listening to music, teaching songs, performing musical-rhythmic movements, dancing, musical-didactic games, teaching children to play musical instruments, and information about music. From each training session, some task of providing musical education to children is solved. The music director leads in this work, shows the right way, gives advice and recommendations. Requirements for children's knowledge and skills are created for each group depending on the type of activity. The difficulty of such activities is that it is necessary to shift children's attention from one activity to another. It is difficult to implement this sequence based on the plan. Considering the psychological characteristics of children, they may forget the works

they learned today the next time. The goal of the modern pedagogic education system is to achieve the general and professional development of a music director belonging to a new category.

Music - aesthetic education, must become a component of the great work being carried out on the path of harmonious education of a person of a democratic society. Musical work with children is especially important. Music evokes a strong emotional feeling in a child's heart. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. In his work "High Spirituality - Invincible Power", Karimov says that "...the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other forms of art on the development of our modern generation in the spirit of high spirituality." they emphasize. Therefore, the art of music and education is a powerful force that develops human qualities in a person, encourages spiritual purification and elevation, enriches the inner world of a person, strengthens faith, will, and awakens creativity - the rise of spirituality. provides. With the help of music, his artistic perception grows and his emotions become richer. It is impossible to raise rich physical, spiritual and moral qualities in children without developing musical perception in children, without sufficiently attracting their love for music. According to the Greek philosopher Plato, the power of the state is directly related to the music, which melody and rhythm it plays. He believed that the country needs music that helps to elevate a person.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Interest in music from a young age has a strong influence on a person's further musical development, ensures the formation of other skills and tastes, and cultivates a good musical taste. Music is a great source of aesthetic and spiritual mood. Taking into account the great influence of music on the child's emotions and formation, on understanding and feeling its content, the appropriate use of a musical work that correctly reflects truth and reality has a special place. The main source of the formation of musical images is directly related to the compatibility of nature and human speech, perception of beauty in the surrounding world.

The tasks of organizing music lessons in preschool educational organizations are as follows:

- ❖ instilling love and interest in music in children of preschool age, educating primary musical taste.
- ❖ development of perception of music, listening ability, aesthetic taste, general culture in children of preschool age.
- ❖ development of musical ability, formation of musical taste, development of artistic creativity in children of preschool age.
- ❖ education of perception of musical works.
- ❖ methods and methods of teaching listening to music, singing, playing musical instruments, musical rhythmic movements.
- ❖ formation of musical ability, emotional attitude to music, ability to listen to music, sense of rhythm.
- ❖ formation of the simplest performance skills in children's music and singing, rhythmic, playing children's musical instruments activities.
- ❖ to develop general musical ability, individual skills, singing voice and expressiveness of movements.

Tasks of musical education:

1. Cultivating love and interest in music.

2. Enriching children's musical experience (based on musical works).
3. Introduce children to simple musical concepts, develop skills in listening to music, singing, and musical rhythms.
4. Formation of emotional feeling in children. Cultivating a sense of melody and rhythm in them.
5. Developing musical taste (based on musical impressions).
6. Development of creativity in children (based on all activities).

Musical works should be selected taking into account the psychological characteristics of children, their interests and worldviews. The pre-school period is called early childhood in psychology and includes the most beautiful and memorable moments of childhood. Music education is taught as part of general subjects in kindergartens and general secondary schools. Today's demand sets specific tasks for preschool educational institutions in terms of providing musical and aesthetic education:

- to make children perceive the beauty of nature, works of art;
- formation of aesthetic taste and feeling;
- teaching to fully understand the concept of beauty in life;
- formation of children's artistic creativity;
- bringing beauty to children into their lives and activities.

Preschool education plays an important role in the continuing education system. Currently, the importance of preschool educational institutions is playing an important role as the first stage of continuous education. Therefore, the importance of separate teaching of each subject is increasing. The main task of every activity in preschool educational institutions is to teach children to think and think. The importance of the art of music is that music is such an art that unites people through their experiences and emotional feelings. It becomes a means of communication between them. It can be called a miracle that the music created by one composer evokes different experiences in the hearts of other people.

Music education is a component of aesthetic education. Education is one of the leading factors that shape a person's personality. Aesthetic education, as its component, is based on the doctrine of the essence of beauty, the unity of aesthetic and moral feelings, the nationalism of art, expands and deepens children's knowledge of the objective world, develops their creative ability and talent. and helps to develop high spiritual qualities in them. It is usually understood that the goal of aesthetic education is to develop aesthetic feelings and thoughts in children, to be able to see and enjoy beauty. In fact, the goals and tasks of aesthetic education are not limited to this. Teaches children to understand and see beauty and ugliness, high and low, joy and sadness. Aesthetic education serves to establish universal and national values. It is clear that education affects a person's mind, feelings, imagination, beliefs, outlook, actions, and behavior.

Let's dwell on the issue of the child's perception of musical works. The art of perception manifests psychological activity after itself, the question of understanding the works of musical art cannot arise by itself. It should be taught. It begins with the feeling of perception of musical works. Perception of musical works creates emotional excitement. In this state of the child, emotions appear on the basis of familiar content and joy. It is necessary to educate the ability of children to understand and accept the work.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, the education of musical perception goes as follows:

1. Extraction of musical material.
2. Systematization of education and training methods.
3. Using different stages of work.
4. Use of various samples of musical works.
5. Gradually becoming more complex depending on the number and form of images of a musical work.

The aesthetic and emotional environment in the world of music creates emotional comfort for the child and forms his interest in creativity. However, the effectiveness of the musical environment depends not only on external conditions, but also on communication, musical-theoretical and psychological knowledge that regulates the child's musical development.

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